

Anti-Anxiety Agents from Natural and Synthetic Origin

Varad Sonawane*, Suvarna Katti

Department of Pharmaceutical Chemistry, Mahatma Gandhi Vidyamandir's College of Pharmacy, Nashik, Maharashtra, India

ABSTRACT

Anxiety represents a heightened emotional response involving persistent fear and worry that disrupts an individual's daily behavior and mental equilibrium. The pharmacological treatments mainly SSRIs, SNRIs, benzodiazepines, tricyclic antidepressants, and MAO inhibitors. Although pharmacological treatments are clinically effective, their use is often constrained by adverse reactions and potential for dependence. Natural products derived from medicinal plants may yield bioactive compounds that demonstrate notable anti-anxiety properties. This review outlines the mechanisms of both synthetic and natural anti-anxiety agents, emphasizing their action on GABAergic, serotonergic, and noradrenergic systems. It also discusses behavioral models for anxiolytic evaluation and the translational gap between preclinical and clinical studies. Furthermore, molecular docking studies using GABA_A receptor structures (PDB ID: 6D6U) illustrate how computational approaches enhance the prediction of receptor–ligand interactions.

Keywords: Anxiety, Anxiolytics, SSRIs, BZDs, SNRIs, MAO inhibitors, TCA, Serotonin transporter (SERT), Animal models, HPA axis, Molecular docking, 6D6U.

INTRODUCTION

Anxiety is a complex emotional condition that evokes affective responses leading to psychological distress and impaired functioning. Persistent or intense anxiety becomes pathological and can contribute to the emergence or worsening of mental and physiological disorders. [1] Expressions of anxiety influence affective-cognitive, vegetative, endocrine, motor, and behavioral levels. Disorders may be defined as chronic states of anxious apprehension that arise devoid of actual danger or stressors, or an exaggerated affective response to regular stimulus. The introduction of DSM-III-R in 1980 redefined diagnostic criteria for anxiety disorders, distinguishing them from broader neurotic categories. [2] As mentioned by Garakani [3], selective serotonin reuptake inhibitors (SSRIs) are used for treatment of anxiety includes benzodiazepines, and atypical antipsychotics, and are approved by FDA. The tricyclic antidepressants (TCAs), monoamine oxidase inhibitors (MAOIs), and mixed antidepressants are frequently used as off-label drugs by the prescribers. The side effects observed are drowsiness, dizziness, fatigue, confusion, and problems with memory or

concentration. Bioactive compounds from herbal, marine, and nutraceutical origins are increasingly being explored for their potential in anxiety management. Traditional medicinal systems such as Ayurveda and Chinese herbal practices have contributed promising leads for anxiolytic compound discovery. Considering the drawback of synthetic drugs and emerging support for natural anxiolytics, a detailed analysis of both classes is imperative. The scope of the current review is to give an account of synthetic anxiolytic agents that are currently in use, to point out potential natural molecules of anxiolytic activity.

2. Anxiety Disorders- An Overview

Classification

On the basis of the clinical picture anxiety disorders can be differentiated into six principal diagnostic subtypes:

a) Panic disorder: Recurrent panic is the hallmark attacks especially when spontaneous. Typically associated with agoraphobia (fear of public places especially where it is difficult to escape).

Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

b) Social anxiety disorder: It is characterized by fear of scrutiny/criticism and symptoms associated with it. e.g., blushing, speech block, trem.

c) Generalized anxiety disorder (GAD): Diagnosed due to excessive and unjustified concern over a wide range of personal and domestic problems, accompanied by symptoms of motor tension, including headache and lethargy.

d) Posttraumatic stress disorder (PTSD): A specific trauma characterized by symptoms which occurs in three areas of brain- (1) hyperarousal symptoms (poor sleep); (2) reemergence of symptoms especially on re-exposure to memories or event; (3) emotional changes such as depression, emotional blunting.

e) Obsessive-compulsive disorder (OCD): Defined by either a compulsive behavior as in checking or washing hands and obsessions that are repeated unwanted intrusive thoughts frequently of negative nature.

f) Simple/specific phobia: A phobia of enclosed spaces, objects, animals or situations like heights.[4]

Neurobiology of anxiety

Neuroanatomy of Fear and Anxiety

Several regions of the medial and orbital prefrontal cortex are implicated in regulating emotional behaviors and modulating anxiety responses. These PFC structures are believed to help understand the more important meaning of experiences, changing how we act based on competing reward and punishment based on what occurs and forecasting social results of behaviors to emotional experiences. These regions exhibit substantial reciprocal connections with the amygdala, enabling modulation of prefrontal cortex neuronal activity and allowing the prefrontal cortex to influence amygdala-mediated reactions to emotionally significant events.[5-12]

Neurochemistry of Fear and anxiety

The neuroanatomical substrates of fear anxiety-related behaviors due to being controlled by a set of chemical systems of neurotransmission. These include the peptidergic neurotransmitters, Corticotropin-releasing hormone (CRH) and neuropeptide Y, substance P, the monoaminergic

transmitters Norepinephrine (NE), serotonin (5-HT), and dopamine. the amino acid transmitters, Gamma aminobutyric acid (GABA) and glutamate.

Role of the noradrenergic system in fear and anxiety

Stressful stimuli enhance central noradrenergic signaling, leading to increased neurotransmitter activity within anxiety-related circuits. The above, therefore, would lead to stress, NE turnover in Locus Coeruleus, in the hypothalamus, in the hippocampus, the amygdala and the cerebral cortex [13]. The firing of LC neurons also increases during fear conditioning and other stressors.[14-16]

Hypothalamic–pituitary–adrenal (HPA) axis and CRH

During stress, the hypothalamic–pituitary–adrenal (HPA) axis triggers the release of cortisol, ACTH, and CRH. Ephemeral increases in plasma cortisol concentration and partial resistance to feedback regulation of cortisol production during and shortly after stressful stimuli can result from this HPA-axis activation during stress. Since high concentrations of glucocorticoids, like those brought on by acute stress, reduce the density of hippocampus glucocorticoid receptors, increasing corticosterone (CORT) release and feedback resistance, this process may include a rapid downregulation of glucocorticoid receptors. When stress ends, glucocorticoid receptor density rises and feedback sensitivity returns as glucocorticoid levels fall (perhaps as a result of less limbic demand on CRH release).[18]

Fig 1: HPA Axis Activation and Glucocorticoid Receptor Regulation During Acute Stress.[19]

GABA/BZD receptor function in anxiety disorders

The central BZD receptor is involved in anxiety disorders on the basis of anxiogenic and anxiolytic properties of BZD agonists and antagonist. This duality suggests that BZD is centrally involve in modulating anxiety. Thesis regarding the role of GABAA/BZD receptor suggests that the complex is a key inhibitory system in the brain. Structural changes in the receptor conformation or alteration in the endogenous ligands could be responsible for pathological anxiety symptoms.[18]

Serotonergic Function in Anxiety

There is inconsistencies in biological markers of serotonin in anxiety. In panic disorder, platelet serotonin intake was reported to be abnormally elevated [20], normal [21] or abnormally reduced [22]. Platelet imipramine binding did not differ in PD did not show significant difference.[23-24] Additionally, studies conducted by Schneider[25], reduced concentration of serotonin in panic disorder compared with control. Although findings were not replicated.

Classification

According to Garakani[3] the synthetic drugs used as anti-anxiety agents are as follows:

1. Selective Serotonin Reuptake Inhibitors (SSRIs):- Fluoxetine, Sertraline, Citalopram, Escitaprolam, Paroxetine, Fluxoamine.
2. Serotonin Norepinephrine Reuptake Inhibitors (SNRIs):- Duloxetine, Venlafaxine, Desvenlafaxine
3. Tricyclic Antidepressants (TCA):- Clomipramine, Imipramine, Desipramine, Nortriptyline
4. Monoamine Oxidase Inhibitors (MAOIs):- Phenelzine
5. Mixed Antidepressants:- Mirtazapine
6. GABAergic drugs:- Pregabalin, Gabapentin
7. Benzodiazepines (BZDs):- Clonazepam, Alprazolam, Lorazepam, Chlordiazepoxide, Oxazepam
8. Antipsychotics:- Trifluoperazine, Olanzapine, Quetiapine
9. Beta-blockers:- Propranolol
10. Antihistamines:- Hydroxyzine

11. Other Anxiolytics:- Busiprone

The plants used as anti-anxiety purpose are as follows [26]:

1. Citrus paradisi var. star ruby (Grapefruit)
2. Cirsium rivulare (Ornamental thistle)
3. Drymaria cordata (Tropical chickweed)
4. Souroubea sympetala
5. Rollinia mucosa (Wild sugar apple)
6. Aethusa cynapium (Dog Poison)
7. Salvia reuterana
8. Cecropia glazioui
9. Passiflora Coerulea
10. Hypericum perforatum
11. Securidaca longepedunculata
12. Albizzia lebeck
13. Protium heptaphyllum
14. Celastrus paniculatus
15. Panax ginseng
16. Paeonia moutan
17. Piper methysticum G. Forster
18. Valeriana officinalis
19. Turnera aphrodisiaca
20. Scutellaria lateriflora

Mechanism of Action**1. Selective Serotonin Reuptake Inhibitors (SSRIs):**

The SSRIs are used as first line drugs in the treatment of generalized anxiety, panic, social anxiety, and obsessive-compulsive disorders. Sertraline and paroxetine are approved for the treatment of PTSD. The reabsorption of serotonin into presynaptic terminals is modulated by Serotonin Transporter (SERT); the neuronal absorption is the chief process by which neurotransmission is terminated. SSRIs function by inhibiting the serotonin transporter (SERT), reducing serotonin reuptake and elevating synaptic serotonin levels. This leads to an increase in extracellular serotonin levels, enhancing and prolonging serotonergic neurotransmission. Ultimately, providing anxiolytic effect. Clinically used SSRIs are more selective for SERT over Nor-Epinephrine Transporter (NET).

Fig 2- Mechanism of Action of SSRIs[27]

2. Serotonin Norepinephrine Reuptake Inhibitors (SNRIs):

SNRIs simultaneously block serotonin and norepinephrine reuptake transporters, thereby enhancing neurotransmission across both pathways. Similar to action of SSRIs, initial inhibition of SERT causes an increase in serotonin levels in the synaptic cleft. This leads to activation of 5HT_{1A} and 5HT_{1D} autoreceptors which are located on presynaptic neuron and acts as negative feedback loop. These autoreceptors are activated when there is rise of serotonin levels due to SERT inhibition. Their activation causes temporary dampening of serotonergic transmission because of reduced serotonin release. With continued treatment, 5HT_{1A} and 5HT_{1D} autoreceptors becomes desensitized which results in weakened negative feedback loop. Allowing serotonin release to resume and increase, improving emotional regulation and relieving anxiety

Fig 3- Mechanism of Action of SSRIs and SNRIs[28]

3. Tricyclic Antidepressants (TCA):

TCAs have an established history in managing of anxiety disorders. However, due to exhibition of serious side-effects they are not generally used as first-line drugs in the therapeutic practice. The pharmacological action of TCA is antagonism of SERT and NET as seen previously in SSRIs and SNRIs. Additionally, TCAs also block other receptors.

4. Monoamine Oxidase Inhibitors (MAOIs):

Monoamine oxidase A and B are widely distributed mitochondrial enzymes. MAO metabolizes monoamine neurotransmitters via oxidative deamination. MAOA preferentially metabolizes 5HT and NE and can metabolize DA; MAOB is effective against 5HT and DA. Although MAOIs exhibit therapeutic efficacy comparable to TCAs, their clinical use is restricted due to significant side effects and drug interactions. The MOAIs agents bind irreversibly to both MOAA and MOAB; thereby inhibiting the capacity to metabolize the endogenous amines such as NE and DA resulting in reduced anxiety symptoms.[29]

5. GABAergic drugs:

The GABA system is another important system in understanding of anxiety disorders. As stated by Gee et al [30], the GABAergic drug Gabapentin primarily acts on $\alpha_2\delta$ Ca²⁺ Channel subunit which is a primary target at which Gabapentin exerts its action. By binding to $\alpha_2\delta$, Gabapentin is thought to alter the calcium channel function thereby reducing influx of calcium ions into presynaptic neurons which ultimately results in reduced hyperactivity of neuronal circuits present in amygdala. By enhancing GABA signaling, it calms the neuronal firing, producing anxiolytic effects.[31]

6. Benzodiazepines (BZDs):

Benzodiazepines act at GABA_A binding specific site which is distinct from GABA binding site. The GABA_A receptor is major inhibitory receptor in CNS. It consists of a transmembrane protein which is composed of five subunits that co-assemble around a central anion-conducting channel. The five subunits come from 19 isoforms, so number of possible

pentameric combinations is high. GABA_A receptor pentamer contains a single benzodiazepine binding site, as well as other allosteric sites at which a variety of sedative-hypnotic-anesthetic agents exert modulatory effects on GABA_A. [32]

Fig 4-GABA_A receptor [33]

The mechanism by which BZDs, such as diazepam (DZP) act is by binding to allosteric site. Allosteric sites are sites other than the principal site that regulate the action of the endogenous ligands. Structure and functional studies have shown that the BZDs binding site is distinct from GABA binding site. Additionally, as demonstrated by Campo-Soria et al [34], that the increase in apparent receptor affinity induced by DZP occurs without a change in closed-state affinity, but by shifting equilibrium toward the high-affinity open state. This means more chloride influx, and reduced hyperactivity of neurons producing anxiolytic effect.

7. Antipsychotics:

Antipsychotics act primarily by antagonizing or modulating D₂ receptors in the brain. Typical antipsychotic agents like haloperidol, chlorpromazine etc. bind tightly and block dopamine diligently leading to pharmacological effects but with various side-effects. Whereas, Atypical agents, such as clozapine, explained by fast-off D₂ theory which states that, these atypical agents bind more loosely and dissociate quickly, allowing normal dopamine transmission to continue and reoccupy receptors thereby exerting an anxiolytic effect. While, reducing side-effects such as Extrapyrimal Symptoms (EPS) and prolactin elevation. [35]

8. Mixed Antidepressants:

Mixed antidepressants exert their anxiolytic effect through enhancing serotonergic and/or noradrenergic transmission in a number of receptor pathways. In contrast to SSRIs/SNRIs, they also impact some serotonin subtypes (5-HT₂, 5-HT₃, 5-HT_{1A}) and other receptors (α_2 , H₁), creating a synergistic action of diminished hyperarousal, enhanced sleep, and greater emotional control—all of which contribute to their anxiolytic effect [36].

9. Beta-blockers:

Beta blockers have fewer uses. They have been prescribed as single-dose agents for performance-related anxiety by musicians as described in James et al [37]. Beta blockers act by antagonizing peripheral and central adrenergic activity which provide calmness in anxiety-provoking situations. As norepinephrine and epinephrine levels are elevated during stress and anxiety states. [38]

10. Antihistamines:

Histamine receptor antagonists such as Hydroxyzine is utilized in the treatment of anxiety disorders. It is widely known that H₁-antihistamines act as inverse agonists that binds with and stabilize the inactive form of the H-receptor, shifting the equilibrium toward inactive state. Thus, effectively antagonize the actions of histamine at H₁-receptors. [39] Its anxiolytic activity can be related to suppression of certain subcortical regions which is demonstrated by Barranco et al. [40]

Methods of evaluation of Anxiolytic Activity

Animal behavior models of anxiety plays a crucial role in the assessment of renowned anxiolytics. There are currently various models utilized of varying complexity and utility for evaluation of anxiolytic agents. They all have in common the use of induced anxiety as an analogy to human anxiety and to give them a basic construct of validity. Most widely utilized screening models include:

A. Elevated Plus Maze (EPM):

The Elevated Plus Maze test is based on the conflict between an animal's exploratory drive and its aversion to open spaces. Observation indicates that open arms provoke fear and avoidance, while closed

arms offer a feeling of safety. The time spent in open versus closed arms indicate the equilibrium between fear and curiosity. Greater exploration in open arms is interpreted as decreased anxiety.

The plus maze setup included pair of open arms, each measuring 16×5 cm, and two closed arms, each measuring $16 \times 5 \times 12$ cm, linked to a central platform (5×5 cm). The height of the maze was raised to a level that was 25 cm above the ground. Every mouse was positioned separately at the core of the EPM, oriented with its head towards an open arm, and monitored for 5 minutes to note the number of entries into the open arm, closed arm, and the time spent in each arm.[41]

Fig 5-Elevated plus maze[42]

B. Open field test:

The model is based on the observation that rodents will naturally tend to explore novel environment, open fields appear to have aversive properties which prevents the exploratory behavior of the rodents. Rodents usually avoid the central areas and prefer peripheral areas. Anxiolytic drugs show greater entries and time spent in centre zone compared to anxiogenic drugs which intensify wall-hugging and decrease exploration.

The open field is a $400 \times 400 \times 300$ mm arena with thin black stripes painted across the floor, dividing it into 16 quadratic blocks. The animals moves from one segment to another, one ambulation is recorded. Also behavior like rearing, standing on hind limbs is also monitored and score is recorded.[41,43]

Fig 6-Open field test[44]

C. Black and White test box

The model is based on the innate behavior of rodents, which show exploratory activity but also have fear of brightly lit, open spaces. Rodents prefer dark enclosed areas, while avoiding brightly-lit areas. Rodents treated with anxiolytics show reduced fear and may explore the White compartment.

A rectangular metal box ($45 \times 27 \times 27$ cm) is positioned above floor level. The box is open at the top and base is divided into 9-cm squares. Two-fifths of the box is painted black and illuminated (with red light of 60 W if specified) and the rest of box is painted white and brightly illuminated with a 60 W light source. Both the compartments are connected via 7.5×7.5 cm opening. Test animals are placed in the box and allowed to move freely. They are primarily observed on 5 behaviors namely rearing, moving within compartments, transition between compartments, period of time spent in each compartment and latency is recorded.[41]

Fig 7: Black and white test box[45]

D. Social-Interaction test

The model primarily relies on unpredictability generated by unfamiliar environment. Two rats are placed simultaneously in the testing environment. Social interaction measures the amount of activities such as grooming, snipping, nipping, crawling, following etc engaged by two rats in a test chamber. The variables affecting anxiety in rodents depends upon intensity of light and the size of field. High light intensity and large arenas increase anxiety whereas, low light and small field decreases the anxiety and increases social interaction. Anxiolytics are expected to increase the amount of social interaction in novel conditions.[41]

Fig 8-Social interaction test in rats

E. Vogel's conflict test

The model is based on principle of conflict behavioral assay, where water-deprived rats are given shock while drinking. The test is used to assess the efficacy of anxiolytic agents by measuring suppression or restoration of punished drinking behavior.

The setup usually consists of a Plexiglas chamber with a metallic grid floor connected to a shock generator. A drinking spout supplying water positioned on a chamber wall. The spout and electric grid are electrically connected so that animal receives a brief shock upon contact. A sensor records the number of licks and a counter displaying number of licks or shock before and after punishment.

This test is convenient to use as this test does not require training of animals. Rats deprived of water for 48 hours are placed in a chamber with water source. In absence of punishment, rats usually lick the water spout virtually without interruption for first 3 minutes of exposure. During conflict sessions, following each 3 seconds of continuous licking, an electric shock of 1 second is delivered through the drinking tube. If shock of 0.8 mili Ampere is delivered drinking is suppressed. If increased punished licking is observed in test drug it is believed to have anxiolytic effect.[41]

Fig 9- Vogel's conflict test setup [46]

Translational Gap in Anxiety Research

Pre-clinical models are insightful in studies of anxiolytic activity. However, as stated by Grillon et al[47] there are several limitations of animal models such as failure to predict human treatment outcomes, failure to stimulate complex cognitive features and subjective human experience in anxiety. Grillon et al also described the need for human experimental models in anxiety which can examine subjective and cognitive dimensions. Furthermore, this model allows testing of treatments and mechanisms that cannot be assessed in animals. The models stated are as mentioned below:

1) Perceptual Sensitivity:

Perceptual hyper-sensitivity is enhanced brain capacity to detect environmental change, a state of hypervigilance is characteristic of anxiety disorders. Mismatch Negativity (MMN) is an event-related potential marking pre-attentive detection of auditory deviation and is generally employed to assess this state. MMN responses are larger in anxious groups, marking higher sensory gain and impaired top-down regulation. Neural studies show this response involves the inferior frontal gyrus and superior temporal gyrus

with increased bottom-up activation and reduced feedback inhibition, demonstrating defective perceptual filtering that is constantly in a state of hyperarousal.

2) Negative Bias:

Negative bias refers to selective processing of aversive or threat-related stimuli. It is characterized by enhanced detection speed of fearful or aversive stimuli on emotional recognition tasks. Neuroimaging illustrates heightened functional connectivity of the amygdala with dorsal anterior cingulate/dorsomedial prefrontal cortex (dACC/dmPFC)—an "aversive amplification circuit" enhancing vigilance for perceived threat. In anxiety disorders, this circuit is abnormally hyperactive even in states of safety, extending pathological vigilance and anticipatory worry. The therapies of SSRIs and cognitive-behavioral therapy (CBT) have been believed to reduce this hyperconnectivity and thereby normalize attention and emotion regulation.

Bridging the Gap by use of Molecular Docking

The persistent gap between animal models of anxiety and human pathophysiological mechanisms. This gap may arise due to difference in physiological properties of animals and humans. Different physiological properties such as receptor structure, pharmacodynamics, and neurocognitive complexity. To overcome these limitations, computational and molecular docking are utilized which enables the visualization and prediction of drug-receptor interactions at molecular level. Such approaches allow design of ligands which are target-specific in nature, thereby improving design, therapeutic relevance and precision.

Molecular docking provides a predictive model for examining how natural or synthetic compounds interact with receptor binding sites at the molecular level and binds to receptor targets such as the γ -aminobutyric acid type A (GABAA). As discussed by Yuriev and Ramsland[48] (2013), docking and molecular dynamics simulations have been instrumental in characterizing the orthosteric (GABA) and allosteric (benzodiazepine and anesthetic) binding sites of GABA receptors.

Integrating molecular docking into anxiolytic research thus provides a mechanistic bridge between in silico predictions and in vivo pharmacological outcomes. Molecular docking represents a key step in closing the gap.

In-silico evaluation of Anti-anxiety activity- Molecular Docking with GABAA Receptor Structure (PDB ID: 6D6U)

GABAA receptor PDB id 6D6U is a heteropentameric composed of $\alpha 1$, $\beta 2$, and $\gamma 2$ subunits, derived from homosapiens. The antianxiety potential of compounds can be evaluated by molecular docking using various softwares like Schrodinger, Autodock-Vina etc. GABAA receptors are part of the superfamily of Cys-loop pentameric ligand-gated ion channels (pLGICs), which include other neurotransmitter receptors, such as the glycine receptor (GlyR). The $\alpha 1$ subunit is the most highly expressed GABAA receptor subunit, and some of its residues have been identified to interact with GABA agonists. It is well known that the aromatic amino acids—phenylalanine (Phe), tyrosine (Tyr), and tryptophan (Trp), are frequently involved in π interactions, which often play an important role in protein structural formation and ligand binding. The six α subunits as well as the $\gamma 2$ subunit and is one of the residues that have been indicated to interact with the GABA agonist [50-55].

The GABAA receptor's benzodiazepine binding region, situated at the junction of the α and γ subunits, binds ligands through a network of π - π stacking, hydrogen bonding and hydrophobic interactions. This structural environment makes the site especially suitable for aromatic and heteroaromatic ligands, where the spatial orientation and electron density of the aromatic system play crucial roles in binding affinity and functional modulation. [56-60] Employing receptor model 6D6U, molecular docking experiments are viable for precise analysis of anxiolytic agents like binding modes, interaction enthalpies. Applying in-silico molecular docking systematic identification of GABA-modulating agents is possible.

Fig 10- Visual representation of receptor 6D6U[49]

CONCLUSION

Anxiety disorders are among the most prevalent mental health conditions, which frequently need long-term medication treatment. While conventional agents like benzodiazepines, SSRIs, and SNRIs remain effective, their limitations including tolerance and dependency highlight the need for safer, natural alternatives. A promising new area is represented by natural anxiolytics made from nutraceutical and medicinal plant sources, which offer bioactive substances with multiple target mechanisms and fewer side effects. Furthermore, advancements in computational approaches such as molecular docking using receptor models like GABAA (PDB ID: 6D6U) have revolutionized drug discovery, enabling precise visualization of ligand–receptor interactions. The integration of computational tools with behavioral and translational approaches offers a rational foundation for designing future-generation anxiolytics that are both efficacious and biologically compatible.

REFERENCES

- Gopala Krishna HN, Sangha RB, Misra N, Pai MRSM. Antianxiety activity of NR-ANX-C, a polyherbal preparation in rats. *Indian J Pharmacol.* 2008;40(4):183-185. doi:10.4103/0253-7613.43153
- Nemeroff CB. Anxiolytics: past, present, and future agents. *J Clin Psychiatry.* 2003;64(suppl 3):3-6.
- Garakani A, Murrough JW, Freire RC, Thom RP, Larkin K, Buono FD, Iosifescu DV. Pharmacotherapy of anxiety disorders: current and emerging treatment options. *Front Psychiatry.* 2020;11:595584. doi:10.3389/fpsyt.2020.595584
- Nutt DJ. Overview of diagnosis and drug treatments of anxiety disorders. *CNS Spectr.* 2005;10(1):49-56. doi:10.1017/S1092852900009901
- Baxter MG, Parker A, Lindner CC, Izquierdo AD, Murray EA. Control of response selection by reinforcer value requires interaction of amygdala and orbital prefrontal cortex. *J Neurosci.* 2000;20(11):4311-9.
- Damasio AR, Grabowski TJ, Bechara A, Damasio H, Ponto LL, Parvizi J, et al. Neural correlates of the experience of emotions. *Soc Neurosci Abstr.* 1998;24:258.
- Rogers RD, Everitt BJ, Baldacchino A, Blackshaw AJ, Swinson R, Wynne K, et al. Dissociable deficits in the decision-making cognition of chronic amphetamine abusers, opiate abusers, patients with focal damage to prefrontal cortex, and tryptophan-depleted normal volunteers: evidence for monoaminergic mechanisms. *Neuropsychopharmacology.* 1999;20(4):322-39.
- Rolls ET. Learning mechanisms in the temporal lobe visual cortex. *Behav Brain Res.* 1995;66(1-2):177-85.
- Garcia R, Vouimba RM, Baudry M, Thompson RF. The amygdala modulates prefrontal cortex activity relative to conditioned fear. *Nature.* 1999;402(6759):294-6.
- Morgan MA, LeDoux JE. Differential contribution of dorsal and ventral medial prefrontal cortex to the acquisition and extinction of conditioned fear in rats. *Behav Neurosci.* 1995;109(4):681-8.
- Öngür D, Price JL. The organization of networks within the orbital and medial prefrontal cortex of rats, monkeys and humans. *Cereb Cortex.* 2000;10(3):206-19.
- Quirk GJ, Russo GK, Barron JL, Lebron K. The role of ventromedial prefrontal cortex in the recovery of extinguished fear. *J Neurosci.* 2000;20(16):6225-31.
- Cassens G, Kuruc A, Roffman M, et al. Alterations in brain norepinephrine metabolism and behavior induced by environmental stimuli

- previously paired with inescapable shock. *Behav Brain Res.* 1981;2(5):387-407.
14. Rasmussen K, Morilak DA, Jacobs BL. Single-unit activity of locus coeruleus neurons in the freely moving cat. I. During naturalistic behaviors and in response to simple and complex stimuli. *Brain Res.* 1986;371:324-34.
 15. Redmond DF Jr. Studies of the nucleus locus coeruleus in monkeys and hypotheses for neuropsychopharmacology. In: Meltzer HY, editor. *Psychopharmacology: the third generation of progress.* New York: Raven Press; 1987. p. 967-75.
 16. Abercrombie ED, Jacobs BL. Single-unit response of noradrenergic neurons in the locus coeruleus of freely moving cats. I. Acutely presented stressful and nonstressful stimuli. *J Neurosci.* 1987;7:2837-43.
 17. Sapolsky RM, Plotsky PM. Hypercortisolism and its possible neural bases. *Biol Psychiatry.* 1990;27:937-52.
 18. Charney DS. Neuroanatomical circuits modulating fear and anxiety behaviors. *Acta Psychiatr Scand Suppl.* 2003;108(s417):38-50.
 19. Perplexity AI. HPA Axis Stress Response Diagram [Internet]. 2025 Oct 7. Generated with Perplexity AI for explanatory purposes.
 20. Norman TR, Judd FK, Gregory M et al. Platelet serotonin uptake in panic disorder. *J Affect Disord* 1986;11: 69–72.
 21. Balon R, Pohl R, Yeragani V et al. Platelet serotonin levels in panic disorder. *Acta Psychiatr Scand* 1987;75: 315–317.
 22. Pecknold JC, Suranyi-Cadotte B, Chang H et al. Serotonin uptake in panic disorder and agoraphobia. *Neuropsychopharmacology* 1988;1:173–176.
 23. Uhde TW, Berrettini WH, Roy-Byrne PP et al. Platelet [3H]imipramine binding in patients with panic disorder. *Biol Psychiatry* 1987;22:52–58
 24. Innis RB, Charney DS, Heninger GR. Differential 3H imipramine platelet binding in patients with panic disorder and depression. *Psychiatry Res* 1987;21:33–41.
 25. Schneider LS, Munjack D, Severson JA et al. Platelet [3H]imipramine binding in generalized anxiety disorder, panic disorder, and agoraphobia with panic attacks. *Biol Psychiatry* 1987;22:59–66.
 26. Kamal M, Jawaid T, HERBAL DRUGS IN MIRROR OF ANXIETY DISORDER -A REVIEW, *IJBR* 2 [1] [2011]62-72.
 27. Source: Mechanism of action of SSRIs: These agents inhibit serotonin transporter causing the... [figure]. ResearchGate. [cited 2025 Oct 5]. Available from: https://www.researchgate.net/figure/Mechanism-of-action-of-SSRIs-These-agents-inhibit-serotonin-transporter-causing-the_fig1_380281339
 28. Source: An illustration depicting the mechanism of action of selective serotonin reuptake inhibitors (SSRIs) and serotonin-norepinephrine reuptake inhibitors (SNRIs) [figure]. ResearchGate. Available from: https://www.researchgate.net/figure/An-illustration-depicting-the-mechanism-of-action-of-selective-serotonin-reuptake_fig1_375253742 (accessed 5 October 2025).
 29. O'Donnell JM, Bies RR, Shelton RC. Drug therapy of depression and anxiety disorders. In: Brunton LL, Hilal-Dandan R, Knollmann BC, editors. *Goodman & Gilman's the pharmacological basis of therapeutics.* 13th ed. New York: McGraw-Hill Education; 2018. p. 267–86.
 30. Gee NS, Brown JP, Dissanayake VUK, Offord J, Thurlow R, Woodruff GN. The novel anticonvulsant drug, gabapentin (Neurontin), binds to the $\alpha_2\delta$ subunit of a calcium channel. *J Biol Chem.* 1996;271(10):5768-76. doi:10.1074/jbc.271.10.5768.
 31. Rose MA, Kam PCA. Gabapentin: pharmacology and its use in pain management. *Anaesthesia.* 2002;57(5):451-62. doi:10.1046/j.0003-2409.2001.02399.x.
 32. Mihic SJ, Mayfield J, Harris RA. Hypnotics and sedatives. In: Brunton LL, Hilal-Dandan R, Knollmann BC, editors. *Goodman & Gilman's The pharmacological basis of therapeutics.* 13th ed. New York: McGraw-Hill; 2018. p.339-52.
 33. Source: Schematic diagram of a GABA_A receptor composition, structure, and binding sites for GABA and benzodiazepines [figure]. ResearchGate. Available from: <https://www.researchgate.net/figure/Schematic-diagram-of-a-GABA-A-receptor-composition->

- structure-and-binding-sites-for-GABA_fig1_333341552 (accessed 5 October 2025).
34. Campo-Soria C, Chang Y, Weiss DS. Mechanism of action of benzodiazepines on GABAA receptors. *Br J Pharmacol*. 2006;148(7):984-90. doi:10.1038/sj.bjp.0706796.
35. Seeman P. Atypical antipsychotics: mechanism of action. *Can J Psychiatry*. 2002;47(1):27-38
36. Farach FJ, Pruitt LD, Jun JJ, Jerud AB, Zoellner LA, Roy-Byrne PP. Pharmacological treatment of anxiety disorders: current treatments and future directions. *J Anxiety Disord*. 2012;26(8):833-43. doi:10.1016/j.janxdis.2012.07.009
37. James IM, Burgoyne W, Savage IT. Effect of pindolol on stress-related disturbances of musical performance: preliminary communication. *J R Soc Med*. 1983;76:194-6.
38. Beale JM, Block JH, editors. *Wilson & Gisvold's Textbook of Organic Medicinal and Pharmaceutical Chemistry*. 12th ed. Philadelphia: Lippincott Williams & Wilkins; 2011. p. 519.
39. Beale JM, Block JH, editors. *Wilson & Gisvold's Textbook of Organic Medicinal and Pharmaceutical Chemistry*. 12th ed. Philadelphia: Lippincott Williams & Wilkins; 2011. p. 737
40. Barranco SF, Bridger W. Treatment of anxiety with oral hydroxyzine: an overview. *Curr Ther Res Clin Exp*. 1977;22:217-27
41. Kulkarni SK. *Practical pharmacology and clinical pharmacy*. 1st ed. New Delhi: Vallabh Prakashan; 2008. p. 49.
42. Source: Illustration of elevated plus maze apparatus [figure]. ResearchGate. Available from: https://www.researchgate.net/figure/Iustration-of-elevated-plus-maze-apparatus_fig1_270161054 (accessed 5 October 2025).
43. Crawley J, Goodwin FK. Preliminary report of a simple animal behavior model for the anxiolytic effects of benzodiazepines. *Pharmacol Biochem Behav*. 1980;13(2):167-70. doi:10.1016/0091-3057(80)90067-2
44. Source: The open field apparatus (A and B) and rotating rod test device (C) [figure]. ResearchGate. Available from: https://www.researchgate.net/figure/The-open-field-apparatus-A-and-B-and-rotating-rod-test-device-C-are-shown-In-order_fig3_264913463 (accessed 5 October 2025).
45. Source: Black & White Test Box (Light–Dark apparatus) [figure]. Bioseb. Available from: <https://www.bioseb.com/en/anxiety-depression-disorder/982-black-white-test-box.html> (accessed 7 October 2025).
46. Figure adapted from: Conflict tasks used to quantify the effects of anxiolytics; (B) Vogel conflict test measuring punished drinking behaviour [figure]. ResearchGate. Available from: https://www.researchgate.net/figure/Conflict-tasks-used-to-quantify-the-effects-of-anxiolytics-A-Conflict-task-used-in_fig1_352840150 (accessed 7 October 2025).
47. Grillon C, Robinson OJ, Cornwell B, Ernst M. Modeling anxiety in healthy humans: a key intermediate bridge between basic and clinical sciences. *Neuropsychopharmacology*. 2019;44(12):2239–2251. doi:10.1038/s41386-019-0445-1.
48. Yuriev E, Ramsland PA. Molecular mechanisms of binding and allosteric modulation in GABAA receptors. *Front Pharmacol*. 2013;4:41. doi:10.3389/fphar.2013.00041.
49. Protein Data Bank. 6D6U: Structure of a human synaptic GABA_A receptor. RCSB PDB; 2018. Available from: <https://www.rcsb.org/structure/6D6U>
50. Barker JS, Hines RM. Regulation of GABA_A receptor subunit expression in substance use disorders. *Int J Mol Sci*. 2020;21(12):4445.
51. Sieghart W, Fuchs K, Tretter V, Ebert V, Jechlinger M, Höger H, Adamiker D. Structure and subunit composition of GABA_A receptors. *Neurochem Int*. 1999;34(5):379–385.
52. Laurie DJ, Wisden W, Seeburg PH. The distribution of thirteen GABA_A receptor subunit mRNAs in the rat brain. III. Embryonic and postnatal development. *J Neurosci*. 1992;12(10):4151–4172.
53. Smith GB, Olsen RW. Identification of a [³H]muscimol photoaffinity substrate in the bovine gamma-aminobutyric acid_A receptor alpha subunit. *J Biol Chem*. 1994;269(33):20380–20387.

54. Westh-Hansen SE, Rasmussen PB, Hastrup S, Nabekura J, Noguchi K, Akaike N, Witt MR, Nielsen M. Decreased agonist sensitivity of human GABA_A receptors by an amino acid variant, isoleucine to valine, in the alpha1 subunit. *Eur J Pharmacol.* 1997;329(2–3):253–257.
55. Westh-Hansen SE, Witt MR, Dekermendjian K, Liljefors T, Rasmussen PB, Nielsen M. Arginine residue 120 of the human GABA_A receptor alpha1 subunit is essential for GABA binding and chloride ion current gating. *Neuroreport.* 1999;10(12):2417–2421.
56. Lavery D, Desai R, Uchański T, Masiulis S, Stec WJ, Malinauskas T, Zivanov J, Pardon E, Steyaert J, Miller KW, et al. Cryo-EM structure of the human $\alpha 1\beta 3\gamma 2$ GABA_A receptor in a lipid bilayer. *Nature.* 2019;565(7740):516–520.
57. Jansen M. An in-depth structural view of a GABA_A brain receptor. *Nature.* 2019;565(7740):436–438.
58. Maramai S, Benchekroun M, Ward SE, Atack JR. Subtype selective γ -aminobutyric acid type A receptor (GABA_AR) modulators acting at the benzodiazepine binding site: An update. *J Med Chem.* 2020;63(7):3425–3446.
59. Golani LK, Yeunus Mian M, Ahmed T, Pandey KP, Mondal P, Sharmin D, Rezvanian S, Witkin JM, Cook JM. Rationalizing the binding and alpha subtype selectivity of synthesized imidazodiazepines and benzodiazepines at GABA_A receptors using molecular docking studies. *Bioorg Med Chem Lett.* 2022;62:128637.
60. Goldschen-Ohm MP. Benzodiazepine modulation of GABA_A receptors: A mechanistic perspective. *Biomolecules.* 2022;12(12):1784.

HOW TO CITE: Varad Sonawane *, Suvarna Katti, Anti-Anxiety Agents from Natural and Synthetic Origin, J. Pharm. Sci., 2025, 1 (10), 435-446. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17372188>

